

Armed Forces, Security Organizations and Nigeria's National Security Challenges: A Case Study

Dr. Orkar, Oryina Michael-David¹, Shaminja, Tersoo, Solomon², Nev, Terwase Timothy³

¹Lecturer, ²Ph.D Research Student, ³Research Student

¹Strategy and Governance Programme, ²Markets and Institutions Programme

³Department of Sociology, University of Abuja, Abuja, Nigeria

^{1,2}Institute of Food Security, Federal University of Agriculture Makurdi, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Nigeria is known as the giant of Africa and for a long time has remained the watchdog of neighboring countries. Nigeria has participated in peace keeping operations in Liberia and Sierra Leone to mention a few. In accordance with its good neighborliness policy, Nigeria has always tried to play a leading role in peace keeping operations. Coming to its domestic issues Nigeria has in the recent past been bedeviled with several security challenges. What readily comes to mind is the readiness and capacity of Nigeria's military and security agencies to maintain Nigeria's military national security. With a view to finding out, this research paper tries to find out whether the military and security agencies have the capacity to maintain Nigeria's national security. It's important to note that the importance of a nation's military national security which has to do with armoury and weaponry basically military preparedness cannot be taken for granted. This paper used survey design to collect data from major states ravaged with major security challenges. Results gathered through empirical evidence show that Nigerian military and security agencies have the capacity to maintain Nigeria's national security. The paper made recommendations towards enhancing the already existing capacity of the military and security organizations to maintain Nigeria's national security.

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KEYWORDS: Armed Forces, Security Organizations and Nigeria's National Security Challenges

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria as a colonial creation of 1960 is considered the most populous Black Country in the world. By virtue of her land area estimated at 923,763sqkm and location which approximates 4°N to 14°N of the equator and longitude of 3°E to 15°E of the Greenwich Meridian (Filani, 1995).

Blessed with abundant natural and human resources, Nigeria is a country to be reckoned with, and in most cases is referred to as the giant of Africa, since the country wills a lot of influence on the other African countries. The dynamics of Nigeria's emergence into nation hood with the attendant long years of military dictatorship have given rise to the emergence and sustenance of several security challenges which the country is bedeviled with today. Military rule in and out of government brought about division and dismayed Nigerians towards recognizing the importance of oneness as a nation. National security and an unfavourable national security policy has further ensured that Nigeria has lagged behind in infrastructural development (Onoja, Mejida and Uhase, 2018). Both internal and external threats and challenges exist in Nigeria's national security and the armed

forces and security organizations are saddled with the responsibility of maintaining national security. The Nigerian armed forces and other security organizations remain important to ensuring territorial integrity and both internal and external security of the nation.

In present day Nigeria, several security challenges exist and this cuts across the length and breadth of the country. This ranges to kidnapping in the southern part of Nigeria, to sectarian and religious crisis in the north-central and north-west part of Nigeria to the Boko Haram terrorist activities in the north eastern part of the country to the Fulani herdsmen attacks that have ravaged most parts of the north-central otherwise known as the middle belt region and some other parts of the northern states. It is on this premise that this research paper is hinged. Nigeria's security challenges are multifaceted and are multinational. The paper is more interested in the military and weaponry aspect of national security. The major objectives of this research paper are:

1. To find out whether Nigerian security agencies have the capacity to maintain Nigeria's national security

2. To observe whether there is an existing relationship between security organizations and Nigeria's national security.

Research Questions

1. Do security agencies have the capacity to maintain Nigeria's national security?
2. Is there any relationship between security organizations and Nigeria's national security?

Research Proposition

This research paper has this as its research proposition. Armed forces and security agencies in Nigeria could have the capacity to maintain Nigeria's national security.

Conceptual Framework/Clarifications Nigerian Security Organization

Nigerian security organizations basically comprise of the Nigerian armed forces, the Nigerian Police Force, the Directorate of State Security Services and the Nigerian Civil Defence Corps. The military is an organization with hierarchy of command and discipline made up of the Army, Navy and Airforce saddled with the maintenance of Nigeria's National Security. To Omede (2012), the military is an organization charged with the complex task of keeping Nigeria one and of protecting the nation from external aggression, the military comprises the army, navy and the air-force. Peterside (2014) observes that the military is one of the most consistent subsectors of the Nigerian federal structure from the time of independence to the present period of democratic re-birth of Nigeria. He also observes that the military is saddled with the primary task of protecting the nation from internal and external aggression. In clarification on Nigeria's military, it is important to note the imperativeness of military strategy. Abubakar (1997) in his submission notes that military strategy is formulated in a manner to be able to fight several wars simultaneously and the same time have the capacity to render assistance to sister internal security agencies in quelling local uprising, and also have the capacity at the same time to participate in peace keeping operations abroad. The military otherwise known as armed forces, are a professional body legally authorized by a sovereign nation state to use weapons to safeguard the country, the Army, Navy, Airforce and in some specific countries the Marines and Coast Guards depending on the geographical locations of the country in question make up the military.

National Security

National security is a concept employed by the military in the defence of the nation. This concept is primarily concerned with the preservation of sovereignty and the independence of nation states. National security is closely related to, often equated and also juxtaposed with, and in fact has revolved from the concept of national interest (Omede, 2012). To Baylis and Smith (2001), National security is freedom from threats to core values of individuals and groups in a given society.

Okoroafor, Nzenwa and Oti (2012) describe national security as the sum of the efforts, energy, intelligence commitment and the use of institutions to enforce and ensure adequate protection of interests, people and property of a nation. It is obvious that a country exists primarily for the protection of lives and property and for ensuring the well-being of the people; therefore, national security refers to the measures taken to ensure survival and safety of the people in the

country (Jekayinfa and Mofoluwano, 2010). Mohammed (2007) describes national security as a condition whereby a country is free from any form of fear or threat to its peace, stability and progress and in the event of any attack, the ability of the country to absorb the shock, get over it and respond effectively to restore public confidence in the state and its institutions. National security is the enablement to preserve, protect and defend the cherished values of a given geographical location which in most cases is either a state within a country or a nation state as a whole. It has to do with enhancement in infrastructural development, poverty reduction, employment opportunities, food security as well as a good build up of weaponry and armoured equipment in preparedness in the event of crisis and war. Both infrastructure and development and build up of weapons go hand in hand to obtain an acceptable standard of national security as both are interdependent.

Theoretical Framework

Frustration and Aggression Theory

Proponents of this theory are John Dollard and Neal Miller et al (1939). More research was carried out and the theory was further expanded in 1962 by Leonard Berthowitz. This theory postulates that the root cause of aggression in society is frustration. Individuals in society's inability to attain their cherished goals leads to frustration.

By inference the occurrence of any aggressive behaviour is always the result of frustration and the more the frustration the more the aggression. A population experiencing alienation and societal injustice also experiences inhuman and unbearable measure which is brought to light in eruption of aggression, these aggression is short termed, or outbursts aimed at those responsible for grievances, hardships and sufferings experienced (Berowitz, 1969). Bringing it home a lot of social vices stare the Nigeria populace in the face. Poverty is on the rise as jobs become scarce by the day. Food security cannot be guaranteed as hunger continue to make the rounds as shelter, food and clothing as basic as they are and some are a challenge to most Nigerians thereby making the vulnerability rate to conflicts, which include terrorism, bombings, kidnapping high as a result of frustration.

A Historical Overview of the Nigerian Armed Forces and Security Organizations

The Nigerian armed forces remain one of the largest and proficient on the African continent. The history of its existence could be traced to 1863, when the Governor of Lagos put together 18 Northern Nigerian's who were expected to protect the British traders, Christian lives and property of British residents in and around Lagos (Miners, 1971). Also, in their preview was to protect British traders, Christian missionaries and to protect the British trade routes around Lagos, basically meaning it was a colonial creation (Ubabi, 1987). The first battalion of the Armed forces was formed 26 August, 1896 while the second and third was formed in 1898 (Buttz and Metz, 1996).

Danomite and Van Doom, (1971) observe that up till 15 January, 1966 the armed forces of Nigeria were seen in public only on ceremonial occasions especially during the annual independence day anniversary every 1st October. George, Shadare and Owoyemi (2012) posit that this practice changed immediately after the January 1966 coup as the armed forces took over managements of Federal, States and to some extent Local Government Councils. Ogah, (2011) in

his opinion notes that, the military is critical element of national defence alongside other security agencies and is saddled with the responsibility of ensuring that the territorial integrity of the Nigerian state and internal security of the nation is assured. He further asserts that development of Nigeria's military power has become urgent due to the transformation of the level of modern day terrorism, Nigeria's rising profile in World Affairs, its regional leadership position and quest for a permanent seat at the United Nations Security Council. The Nigerian Army is the land branch of the Nigerian armed forces and the largest among the armed forces, while the Nigerian Navy is the sea branch of the Nigerian Armed forces. Its command structure consists of Naval Headquarters, three operational commands, one training command, training facilities spread all over Nigeria, five operational bases, five forward operational bases two dockyards and two fleet (Fayemi, 2003). The Nigerian Air Force was established with technical assistance from West Germany. The Nigerian airforce flies transport, trainer, helicopter and fighter aircraft (Fayemi, 2003).

Amonda, (2013) notes that though the structure of the armed forces was for subjugation, domination and to safeguard the sovereignty of the independence populace, the structure has been modified and modernized over the past five decades, though its functional capability has remained unaltered. He further asserts that the Nigerian armed forces has successfully been used for pacification of rebellious and restive populations as well as contributed both equipment and troops for peace keeping support both regionally and globally.

The Nigerian Police Force began with a thirty member consular guard formed in Lagos colony. In 1879 it had 1,200 members. The Police are a unit of the forces established for the maintenance of law and order. It is a branch and department of government charged with the preservation of public order and tranquility, enforcement of laws, the promotion of public peace, safety and morals, the prevention, detection and prosecution of offenders (Okereke, 2012).

Though the Nigerian Police force is still dragging its feet in obtaining an optimum level of a corruption free force, it remains the closest ally in maintaining a crime free, peace and order in the Nigerian society. Dabanzau (2007) attests to this fact when he observes that, though the Nigerian Police force is bedeviled with a lot of inadequacies the force still remains the biggest, most viable and most important subsector of the criminal justice system either through reports or self-discovery. It is unfortunate that the inherent nature of man is criminal in nature, the Holy Bible also agrees with this by saying that the heart of man is desperately wicked. Ehindero, (1998) observes that the word police originates from the Greek word polis meaning the part that has to do with the health and society of the people. The Nigerian police force is structured along the Federal system of government. The inspector-general being the head at the Federal level, the commissioner of police at the state levels and the divisional police officers at the local government levels, just like in other sectors of Nigerian institutions, the Nigerian police force has its own fair share of issues which include problems associated with shady recruitment, lack of equipment and training, inefficiency, indiscipline, lack of expertise of the job, corruption and low

level of public confidence. Furthermore, the police seem more at home with paramilitary operations and the exercise of force rather than functions of crime prevention, detection and investigation. (Obaro, 2014). The directorate of state services popularly known as the DSS was created in 1986 under the Babangida regime as was formally known and called the National Security Organization (NSO). The organization's responsibility is primarily to cater for internal security of the nation Intelligence (Intelligence Profile: Nigeria, 2003). The mission statement of the DSS is basically to protect and defend the Federal Republic of Nigeria against domestic threats, uphold and enforce criminal laws of Nigeria and to provide leadership and criminal justice services to both Federal and State law enforcement organs (Intelligence Profile: Nigeria, 2003). The organization has been able to crackdown on kidnapping and has also infiltrated a number of religious extremist groups (Intelligence Profile: Nigeria, 2003). The Nigerian Civil Defence and Security Corps is a paramilitary agency of the Federal Republic of Nigeria commissioned to provide measures against any state and its citizens. (NSCDC, 2019). In line with Nigeria's security as a nation state, the defence policy serves as a guideline to operations of armed forces and security organizations existing in the country. Alemika, (2000) asserts that Nigerians are concerned about their security and rights and expects that Nigerian armed forces and security establishments should be able to guarantee this. While on the other hand, Tar (2009) posits that there seems a disconnect between the military, police and other paramilitary establishments and he suggests the need for a new security architecture that constructs all military and paramilitary agencies hitherto security organizations as equal partners in the task of keeping the nation secure. He suggests their harmonization into a commission to harmonize and take care of all military and para-military agencies. The cooperation and harmonization of Nigerian security agencies will contribute positively on improving the already existing security apparatus which will for sure go a long way in improving Nigeria's military national security status.

Material and Methods

Research Design

This research study adopted survey design. This method was used since it is suitable for obtaining information from several respondents cutting across all barriers and data collected can be used to generalize.

Study Area

The study area is north eastern Nigeria. The northern part of Nigeria comprises of Borno, Adamawa, Yobe, Gombe, Bauchi and Taraba state. Among these states, three states were chosen randomly namely Borno, Adamawa and Yobe. The population of Borno state is 4,151,193 (NBS, 2012). Population of Yobe state is 2,321,339 (NPC, 2017) and the population of Adamawa state is 3,168,100 (LGIDD, 2012).

Population of Study

The population targeted for this study was residents of the various areas which include farmers, politicians, security experts and academics. The total population of the study area which was made up of Borno, 4,151,193, Adamawa, 3,168,101 and Yobe 2,321,17 respectively made total population of representation for the study stand at 9,640,633.

The statistical formula used to determine the sample size was calculated with a confidence level of 96%. This formula was used since the population size of the study area is known.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

where

n = sample size

N = total population

e = acceptable error link or margin error

thereby n = 9640663

$$e = 4\% = 0.04$$

$$(e)^2 = 0.0016$$

$$n = 9640663 \frac{9640663}{1 + 9640663 (0.0016)}$$

$$n = \frac{9640663}{1 + 9640663 (0.0016)}$$

n = 624

Rounded to the nearest n=600 (Rounded).

Therefore, the sample size for the study was rounded to 600 given an equality of 200 per state this was for easier distribution as well as equal representation.

Instrument for data collection

The instrument for data collection used for this study was a questionnaire comprising of both open and close ended questions. Numbers of questionnaires administered were 600 though 577 copies were returned. This gave a success rate of 97%.

Method of Data Analysis

Simple percentages were used to answer or disprove the research proposition. The data was computed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

Research Findings/Discussion of Findings

Research Proposition

Security Agencies in Nigeria could maintain Nigeria's National Security.

Table: Percentage on Armed forces and security agencies can maintain Nigeria's national security.

Responses	Frequency	Percentage %
SA	161	27.8
A	271	46.8
D	111	19.2
SD	39	6.8
Total	579	100

Source: Field Survey, 2018

The table above reveals that 161 respondents representing (27.8%) strongly agree that Nigerian security agencies can maintain Nigeria's national security, while 271 respondents representing (46.8%) also agree that Nigerian security agencies can maintain Nigeria's national security. The 111 respondents representing (19.2%) disagree and 39 respondents representing (6.8%) strongly disagree that Nigerian security agencies can maintain Nigeria's national security. From the above analysis it thereby implies that

Nigerian armed forces and security agencies are capable of maintaining Nigeria's national security. Based on the simple percentage result calculated, from the above table, 27.8% of the total respondents strongly agree while 46.8% agree bringing the total sum to 74.6% in the table of simple percentages. The proposition has therefore, been confirmed. This means that the armed forces and Nigeria's security agencies have the capacity to maintain Nigeria's national security. This finding agrees with the work of Eze and Aguanwo (2014) who report that Nigerian military and security agencies have capacity to maintain Nigeria's national security. This can be seen in the deployment of 3,600 security personnel to Maiduguri and other major north east towns as part of the Joint Task Force (JTF) a special formation of the military, police and the state security services unit. In his report Garba (2015) indicates that the Nigerian government has increased its troop's deployment of military and security personnel as well as improvement in the supply of arms and equipment to the military and has also made efforts to mobilize greater international support and cooperation. Also, in agreement Omeri, (2014) reports that the federal government of Nigeria has equipment to maintain national security, since the military is more equipped and more combat ready as its men have been trained in the use of modern security gadgets and equipment and have been deployed to secure the nation especially in the area of fighting the Boko Haram terrorist as well as other evolving threats to national security with the view of bringing perpetrators to justice. Alli (2016) also agrees with the findings when he reported that the United States government has donated armoured equipment valued at 11 million and also provided consultancy on intelligence training and logistic support under its excess defence articles programme to further boosts Nigeria's military and security agencies capacity to maintain Nigeria's national security.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This research study looked at the origin of the military and security organizations in Nigeria with constitutional rules in relation to capacity to maintain Nigeria's national security. National security in this paper is concentrated on the aspect of military national security which is narrowed down to weaponry, arms, ammunition and readiness for war in preparedness to safeguard the territorial integrity of Nigeria both internally and externally. This paper had the view towards finding out whether the military and security organizations have the capacity to maintain Nigeria's national security challenges. The findings show that the military and security agencies in Nigeria have the capacity to maintain Nigeria's national security with the literature reviewed it is clear that there is an existing relationship between the military, security agencies and Nigeria's national security.

Based on the result of the findings, the following are recommended;

1. There is the need for capacity building, training and retraining with the view to improve upon the already existing capacity of the military and security organizations, this should be done jointly so that all the security organizations can benefit maximally.
2. Sustained cooperation and harmonization of both the military and security organizations must be encouraged and adhered to with the view of increasing efficiency with them being interdependent without any seeing itself as more important and looking down on the other.

This will further build up and increase the already existing capacity.

3. Welfare issues of personnel should be prioritized at all times in order to motivate and boost the morale of personnel for optimal productivity and performance.
4. Security related challenges such as poverty, unemployment and illiteracy should be made top most priority of government at all levels in Nigeria to reduce internal and external national security threats.

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